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Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE & RESILIENT VALUE CHAINS

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Authors

ERDN - LAEI | Dr. Živilė Gedminaitė-Raudonė and Dr. Rita Lankauskienė

Contributors

Lithuanian MAP experts

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1. Summary and key messages

Rural citizens, type of activities in rural regions, and the whole rural areas in Lithuania have faced considerable changes in recent decades as in the whole Europe. Several key factors have been at the origins of such changes, ranging across economic and demographical changes, technological development, socio-economic changes, and policy developments at national and at the EU level.

The biggest challenge is that rural communities need to find their role in this changing situation. Based on previous discussions at the time of preparation of the Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development of Lithuania for 2023–2027 among representatives from science, policy, and society in Lithuania, the new focus is strengthening the local economy, creating inclusive local infrastructure and services, smart governance and smart rural community, environment protection and climate change mitigation.

This Position paper “Towards Sustainable & Resilient Value Chains” provide needs, challenges and policy intervention that are already in place and needed for the future when we assess entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains of rural regions of Lithuania.

2. Introduction

In 2022, the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) of Lithuania has decided to continue to work on “entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, and sustainable & resilient value chains”. This topic is a follow-up of the topic “change in production and diversification of the rural economy” covered by 8 MAPs in 2021 and it is related to the “Prosperous rural areas” strand of the Long-Term Vision for rural areas in the EU. This topic covers issues related to employment, reskilling, upskilling, entrepreneurship, and short supply chains & sustainable value chains.

Inhabitants of rural regions, activities and the whole rural areas have faced considerable changes in recent decades in Lithuania as in the whole Europe. Several key factors played a major role in these adjustments such as economic and demographical changes, technological development, socio-economic changes and policy developments at national and at the EU level. In Lithuanian key strategies for the development of rural areas are currently concerned with the diversification of economic activities in these territories. It highly depends on the selected approach towards diversification itself and the state of common understanding of the critical concepts in the context of rural development, namely ‘smart rurality’, ‘smart communities’, ‘digitalisation’, ‘bio-economy’, ‘sustainable management of resources and ‘food chain’.

The MAP Position Paper provides answers to the following key questions:

- What are the needs of the area covered by the MAP in relation to entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains?
- What are the policy interventions already in place, and what are examples of actions taken by local actors addressing these needs implemented on the area covered by the MAP?
- Which policy interventions (i.e. instruments, measures) are recommended by MAP members to be implemented at the local, regional, and/or national level? How can the EU support these interventions?
- What are the knowledge gaps and what research projects are needed?

The position paper was prepared using a six-step Delphi method, combining research, and use of quantitative data with expert interviews and surveys. The following six steps were applied for this paper: (1) Desk research and context analysis (March-April 2022); (2) Interviews at the Focus group meeting (May 2022); (3) Interview analysis, writing MAP Position paper and preparation of survey (May-July 2022); (4) MAP survey

(August 2022); (5) Survey analysis (September 2022); (6) Validation of results (Consensus meeting: September 22, 2022).

The MAP of Lithuania is part of the "Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania" (CBioLit). This platform is coordinated by the Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Institute of Economics and Rural Development. The SHERPA project defines a MAP as "*the forum for two-way exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge with actors at European and regional levels*". Lithuanian MAP covers the whole territory of Lithuania. "Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania" (CBioLit) is a newly established platform. The quadruple helix approach was used to identify active members of the MAP of Lithuania "Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania" (CBioLit): science (universities and research institutes); society: private sector and civil society organisations (NGOs); policy (public sector).

The MAP of Lithuania "Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania" (CBioLit) focuses on 3 broad fields of RIS3 strategy:

- Agro-innovation and food technologies. Priority "*Safer food and sustainable usage of biomaterials*".
- Inclusive and creative society. Priority "*Modern self-development technologies and processes promoting the formation of creative and promotive individuals*".
- Energy and sustainable environment. Priority "*Energy and fuel production using biomass/waste and waste treatment, storage and disposal*".

Keywords: rural areas, entrepreneurship, sustainable and resilient value chains, social economy, rural communities, LAGs.

3. Current situation based on background research and evidence

Various scientific evidence and data had been examined to perform a background research in the field of entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, and sustainable & resilient value chains in Lithuania. The main aim of this research was to pre-identify the key factors shaping the Lithuanian experience in the selected topic of interest. The four key areas were in-depth analysed to compose a sufficient background for further elaboration within Lithuanian MAP:

1. Prerequisites for entrepreneurship and social economy in Lithuanian rural areas;
2. Retraining and upskilling;
3. Farming conditions and young farmers;
4. Farmers' position in the changing value chains and prospective developments.

Prerequisites for entrepreneurship and social economy in Lithuanian rural areas. Macro data shows that the number of farms in Lithuania has been declining rapidly: over the period 2010-2016, the number of farms decreased by almost one quarter, from 199.9 to 150.3 thousand (Agricultural Census, 2012; Farm Structure Survey, 2016). Detailed analysis on the changes of farm structure (by the size of agricultural land under management) shows that the fastest growth was observed in the number of large farms with more than 100 ha (39 % increase), whereas the number of small farms with less than 10 ha fell the most (31 % decrease).

According to the latest comparable statistics of economic activity in Lithuania over the years 2015-2019 (Statistics Lithuania, 2022), the activity rate both in rural and urban areas increased by 3%. In 2015, the activity rate was 54.9% in rural and 61.2% in urban areas of Lithuania, and in 2019 it reached 57.9% in rural and 64.2% in urban areas. Over the same period, the employment rate have also increased, however, it should be still considered as having a potential to further raise especially in rural areas. Indeed, in 2015, employment rate counted 47.1% in rural and 57.0 % in urban areas, and in 2019 it reached 53.0% in rural,

and 60.8% in urban areas. The total labor fluctuated differently in urban and rural areas in Lithuania during the analysed period. In 2015, the total labor force in Lithuania counted 447.8 thousand people in rural areas (of which employed 384.1, unemployed 63.7 thousand) and 1021.1 thousand people in urban areas (of which employed 950.8, unemployed 70.3 thousand). In 2019, the total labor force in rural areas increased to 452.3 thousand people (of which employed 414.1, unemployed 38.2 thousand), whereas in urban areas decreased to 1018.1 thousand people (of which employed 964.4, unemployed 53.7 thousand). The initial analysis suggests that people in rural areas might use (or even are already using) different possibilities, support schemes, and skills for starting new entrepreneurial activities in rural areas and creating new sustainable value chains.

Farmers' incomes remain a key determinant of their decision to operate in the sector, creating the preconditions for entrepreneurship, social economy, and value chains. The number of farms is declining and it is therefore important to ensure the attractiveness of the agricultural sector in terms of income. Income stability in agriculture is increasingly difficult to ensure. This is due to the fact that economic performance is not only dependent on unpredictable output prices but also, increasingly, on extreme natural events. The shrinking number of farms threatens to undermine food security.

Retraining and upskilling. Retraining and up-skilling in Lithuania are tightly connected to changes in market orientation and the demand for improving competitiveness. Both these factors form a new way of understanding value chains and their sustainability. Recent food trends are changing the way agriculture and food are traded. For instance, consumer responsibility seeking for the sustainable use of natural resources is growing. People believe more and more that transporting food over long distances increases CO₂ emissions. They also believe that food transported from afar has a long shelf life and is therefore produced with various preservative additives and fruit and vegetables are treated with chemicals. In addition, freshness and naturalness of food are becoming more and more important to consumers when choosing food products in Lithuania. Buying local food also make consumers feel more socially responsible and contributing to the economic potential of rural communities. New consumer preferences have resulted in the rise of food purchased directly from farmers and hence of a new concept of 'food as a service' provided by farmers to consumers. In such a market, importers are unable to compete with local producers.

Product and process innovations are essential to improve farm competitiveness through diversification of farm activities. Competitiveness should not only be enhanced through technological innovation in agri-food production. Recently, the bioeconomy has been identified as one of the priority areas for development, and the production of high-value-added products using biomass is therefore promising. In Lithuania, advanced innovations have not yet been implemented at the necessary scale. Hence, parameters such as education, the age and readiness of farm operators, and advice are important for diversification in rural areas (Eurostat, 2022; Statistics Lithuania, 2022).

Farming conditions and young farmers. Lately, it was increasingly recognised, that the 'new quality' of sustainable value chains might be arranged only with help of the young generation and innovative farmers as they can change the existing imperatives and operate in rural areas considering the sustainability and green transformation issues. From this point of view, it is necessary to ensure sufficient support for young farmers via financial mechanisms. According to the latest data, the need for investment support for young farmers through subsidies exceeded the available budget. Around 50% of the young farmers who applied for a subsidy to establish a farm were rejected. According to the internal unpublished data from the Lithuanian Ministry of Agriculture (2022), the requested sum for investment in 2020 was € 129.4 million, and the amount of aid disbursed was € 55.8 million. The number of applicants in 2020 was 2754, and funding was received only by 1355 applicants. In total, between 2014 and 2020, € 339.9 million of the Rural Development Programme support for economic and business development in Lithuania was allocated among the four core activities, and 75% of these was support for investments for the creation and development of economic activities (National Paying Agency, 2020). Among the reasons for which young farmers cannot receive sufficient funding for investment, too high risk for investment and unfavourable bank policy is one of the main ones (fi-kompass, 2020).

Farmers' position in the changing value chains and prospective developments. Changing consumer needs have led farmers to search for new ways to participate in the market (Vidickiene et al., 2018; Lankauskiene et al., 2022). In Lithuania, there have been a growing number of initiatives to develop a local food system and short food supply chains, using a variety of direct sales methods for agricultural and food products: mobile and stationary farmers' markets, farm shops, direct sales from farms, pre-ordering and delivery systems and other forms of partnership between producers and consumers.

In the country, many different projects have been implemented to develop short food supply chains. The "Cheesemakers' House" is one of the successful examples (see Picture 1.).

Picture 1.

Source: <http://www.surininkunamai.lt/>; <https://www.facebook.com/SurininkuNamai.lt/>.

Despite the many positive developments, the remaining problem is the volumes of direct sales, which are not high. Their development is hampered by various obstacles, the most important of which are (Vidickiene & Gedminaitė-Raudonė, 2016):

- Lack of knowledge, initiative and skills to start a new direct sales activity;
- Shortcomings in legal regulation;
- High veterinary requirements, limited access to finance;
- Limited range of products and insufficient quantities, seasonality of production;
- Lack of cooperation and collaboration;
- Complex public procurement regulation for the supply of agricultural and food products to public sector bodies and institutions.

Based on these pre-defined conditions for entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, and sustainable value chains, the Lithuanian further discussed to find out what are currently the hottest issues for the expansion of resilient value chains in the country, and what future developments are on-demand.

4. Position of the Multi-Actor Platform

This section summarises the opinion and suggestions of the Lithuanian MAP experts on needs, challenges, opportunities, policy interventions, potential knowledge gaps, and recommendations concerning the entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, and sustainable & resilient value chains within the country.

4.1. Identified needs

Smart rurality, smart villages, digitalisation, bioeconomy & short supply chains are main keywords for the expected future of rural areas in Lithuania and are also defined in the new development programme of Lithuania for 2023–2027 (Strategic plan 2023–2027 for Agriculture and Rural Development of Lithuania, 2022). The MAP Position paper on the long-term vision for Lithuania (2020) highlighted that “*rural areas of Lithuania up to 2040 are rural regions with modern villages in partnership as an attractive place to live and work*”. Smart villages – alongside with their strategy for development where communities of farmers, craftsmen, and other businesses- live, work and invest by applying principles of cooperation using renewable resources to produce local products and sell them to consumers. Such principles ensure the protection of biodiversity as well as the creation and preservation of rich landscapes (Gedminaitė-Raudonė, Vilke, 2020).

Identification of needs by MAP experts was based on critical factors and driving forces required for sustainable rural development suggested by Akgün et al. (2015): physical system, social system, economic system, locality system and creative system (Akgün et al., 2015). Information is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The critical factors and driving forces required for sustainable rural development.

Source: Akgün et al., 2015.

Three questions were identified among experts to reflect how these 5 critical factors and driving forces are being implemented in rural areas of Lithuania:

1. Who will take the main role in the implementation of activities important for physical, social, economic, locality and creative systems?
2. What are new needs and their compliance with already existing initiatives?
3. What recent challenges are the most important for rural areas?

Actors in the development of rural areas in Lithuania. There are several groups of actors that play a significant role in the development of rural areas in Lithuania on (1) individual level, such as residents, farmers, etc.; (2) on the organisational level, such as rural communities, LAGs, associations, public organisations (including municipalities and ministries). Local residents, given their role of individuals or members of organisations, are key players in the implementation of actions that meet the current needs and follow rules that are set in development programmes and supervised by public organisations (as the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, National Paying Agency). Leaders and entrepreneurs are the engine for many other rural residents and act as motivators. It was agreed among experts that rural communities and local action groups (LAGs) take a very important role as intermediaries between local residents and public organisations that are responsible for rural policy implementation and coordination in Lithuania. Experts also mentioned that the involvement of scientists and consultants in the management of change in rural areas is essential. In addition, involving youth in rural transformation is very important to make a durable change. During a survey, it was also mentioned that country clubs, communities contributing to activities in their homeland, and townspeople with homesteads in the countryside might play a significant role in the development of rural areas in Lithuania.

Actors of Lithuanian rural areas are driving forces of 4 out of 5 elements, as proposed by Akgün et al. (2015):

- In social system by creating social relations, using principles of openness and networking with actors within and outside community and by participating in various initiatives;
- In economic system by strengthening leadership, entrepreneurship, human capital, and increasing economic diversity;
- In locality system with the possibility to use tacit knowledge and employ/strengthen natural and cultural capital;
- In creative system by conversion of local knowledge and finding ways how to use/increase the use of technologies.

There are many examples of new attractive and successful initiatives in the Lithuanian countryside over the last decades. Experts have also highlighted that rural communities are the heart and engine of rural areas in Lithuania.

New needs and existing initiatives. In Lithuania, expectations and needs for rural areas in the new CAP (2023-2027) are defined with keywords such as 'smart rurality', 'creation/strengthening of smart villages', an increase in digitalisation, and short supply chains.

Mapping key steps from 2004 - when Lithuanian joined the EU - different initiatives and actions were named as a road towards today's future:

- 1st step. Past (from 2007 to 2013). Gathering of experience for rural residents and communities. Rebuilding, renovating, constructing and empowering community buildings (*first businesses* initiated by rural communities) and improvement of other infrastructure necessary for high-quality living in rural areas.
- 2nd step. Present (from 2014 to 2020). Gathering of new ideas. Creation of *social and community businesses*.
- 3rd step. Future (from 2021 to 2027). Smart villages in Lithuania.

Implemented over the 2007-2013 period, the 1st step was important as a critical factor and driving force required for sustainable rural development related with "Physical system": renovation and creation of infrastructure important for rural residents. The 2nd step, implemented between 2014 and 2020, was important as a critical factor and driving force for the "Economic system" and "Locality system": starting new business initiatives by rural communities. 3rd step is important as activities for the future, related with the remaining "Creative system" and "Social system": increase of social and community business, actions towards smart villages.

Implementation of actions toward sustainable rural development had not only caused positive changes but also opened up new challenges. The following recent challenges were identified by the experts concerning the entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, sustainable and resilient value chains in Lithuania:

1. Lack of trust from public authorities in rural communities and LAGs. This is related to activities on project implementation by rural communities and LAGs.
2. High bureaucratic burden. It decreases initiatives from rural inhabitants and/or communities.
3. Availability and amount of voluntary time spent on rural community initiatives. Not enough financial resources to cover the costs of personnel who prepare and implement projects by LAGs in rural areas. It can be expected to receive good project results when you have a sufficient amount of time and worse results with a lower amount of time spend on it.

All three challenges were identified as very important by all experts, however, the high bureaucracy burden, especially from the local to a national level was mentioned repeatedly almost in all implemented discussions by the Lithuanian MAP. Among the other challenges, also particular attention was put on:

- Shifting from non-renewable to renewable resource production and consumption;
- Equal partnerships in rural change management decisions;
- Use of IT in managing rural change;
- Ageing of rural communities;
- Problems in generational renewal; and
- Lack of new ideas.

Among the recent needs of rural communities in Lithuania, the most important are:

1. Trust in the setup and implementation of actions and projects from public authorities to rural communities and LAGs.
2. Use of opportunities for networking and cooperation. Steps to create real cooperation and not only an image of it.
3. Quality of services in rural areas. Optimisation of costs needs to find other solutions (closing of schools, post offices, hospitals, etc.). Role of rural communities in the provision of basic services initiated by public authorities as new functions (logistic, administration, management, etc.).
4. Steps to decrease bureaucratic burden, especially for LAGs.
5. Search for solutions to motivate leaders of rural communities aiming to revert the decrease in interest and progressive demotivation.
6. Creation of 'Smart Village' strategies that will reflect the challenges and needs of their territory by building on their local strengths and assets.
7. Care of communities as cells of body aiming good functioning of it.
8. Guidelines for implementation of the 'Smart villages' concept in Lithuania.

Among the other needs, it was mentioned, that quality of services in rural areas does not have to mean that all services are located in the countryside, e.g. a hospital or a school, but it must be ensured that rural people have easy access to qualitative services in the city. This is where the importance of logistics services comes in. There has been a call to remember that Lithuania is not so rich and hence that not every rural town can have a qualitative school, highly qualified doctors, etc.. It was also mentioned that there is a need for mobile and virtual services as a solution to ensure quality services are received in remote places. It was also suggested that funding should be proposed for community activities aimed at improving social skills not only for community members but also for other local people to increase social inclusion.

Finally, the aim of smart villages was introduced: the aim of smart villages in Lithuania is searching smart solutions for rural areas that meet the needs of local residents by creating long-term vision, based on ideas proposed by scientists and innovative technologies. The principle of 'being smart' focuses on the increase of attractiveness of rural areas, entrepreneurship, and creation of necessary infrastructure, use of cooperation and creation of stronger relations with neighbours. One expert stated that 'being smart' can be understood as 'receiving what you want' and 'achieving what you need'. This principle can reflect the needs of all actors that take part in the development of rural areas. It was stressed that 'smart solutions' firstly require a proactive local leader who is paid to be creative and who is able to solve local community problems with creativity and intelligence, and also that integrate a smart application of LEADER principles.

Smart solutions require (1) thinking 'out of the box' (non-standard way); (2) starting from yourself; (3) enough time for creativity; (4) critical situations (example can be with the recent pandemic situation – it has opened up many new opportunities as before communities were not even thinking that some challenges can be overcome in one or another way).

4.2. Existing interventions and actions

Since 2007, more focused interventions and actions to support entrepreneurship and social economy just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains in rural areas of Lithuania have started. Main support tool for LAGs and rural communities is LEADER programme, which is part of the Rural development programme for Lithuania. The Lithuanian Network of LAGs plays an important role as this association, established in 2007, gathers 49 Lithuanian rural LAGs. LAGs, are umbrella non-governmental organisations implementing the LEADER initiative in rural areas. Activities and role of LAGs are provided in table below.

Local action groups encourage residents and organisations to actively participate in local and community development processes, help strengthen civil society, and support harmonious cooperation between local government, business, and the non-governmental sector.

The mission of the LAG network is to promote national and international cooperation between local action groups, to represent common interests in order to successfully implement the LEADER approach and innovative rural development at the European, national and regional levels. Collect and disseminate information, solve problems related to the activities of LAG network members, share knowledge, experiences, achievements and ideas.

LAG network functions:

1. Defending and representing the interests of the members of the LAG network.
2. Consulting.
3. Participation in the process of drafting Lithuanian and European Union legal acts that may affect the activities of the Network members.
4. Collection and dissemination of information.
5. Formation of a good image of LAG network members in society.
6. Preparation of proposals for the improvement of the administration of the LAG network members.

Source: LAG Network, 2022.

From 2007 to 2022, more than € 118 million investments have been channelled by the LEADER Programme in Lithuania. The number of projects financed was approximately 3885, whereas the establishment of new job opportunities was estimated to be more than 2000. Budget for 2014–2020 period was € 113,5 million. In the new programming period, the planned budget equals to € 75 million, which makes this budget comparatively lower than in the past (see picture below).

European agricultural fund for rural development (EAFRD) and national budget		
Funding of LEADER programme in 2014-2020	Funding of LEADER programme in 2021-2022 (transitional period) + 21 million EUR	Funding of LEADER programme in 2023-2027
113,5 million EUR		+75 million EUR

Source: Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, 2022.

In the period from 2023 to 2027, five topics have been selected by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania to foster entrepreneurship and social economy in rural areas, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains in Lithuania:

1. Projects for local economy:
 - a. Economic diversification and rural tourism;
 - b. Short supply chains and local food systems.
2. Projects for creation of inclusive local infrastructure and services:
 - a. Social networks and other e-platforms for information exchange, e-public services;
 - b. Social service centres, the House of Generations;
 - c. Science-based innovative education, training and consultation;
 - d. Solutions for smart green infrastructure.
3. Projects for smart governance:
 - a. Provision of public administration services remotely (on-line);
 - b. Digitalised work of community and feed-back using digital tools;
 - c. Development of organisational reflexes, optimisation of activities and increase of efficiency.
4. Projects for smart rural community:
 - a. Ability to accumulate and use local intangible resources for the benefit of local residents and business development;
 - b. Digital skills and use of digital technologies;
 - c. Cooperation and networking; development of management tools for cooperation.
5. Projects for environment protection and climate change mitigation:
 - a. Sustainable use of natural resources and restoration (smart use);

- b. Solutions to solve food wasting problems;
- c. Waste management;
- d. Renewable energy;
- e. Agroecology and agro-environment.

Criteria for selection of new projects are aligned to the above-mentioned aims: strengthening entrepreneurship, cooperation and social economy of rural areas. In particular, new projects that embed one of the following items will be prioritised 1) more partners in the project for a wider cooperation (partnership with different actors from LAGs, sectors and project leaders); 2) green transformation, environmental issues (within the project); 3) investments from other funding sources; 4) use of digital solutions; 5) creating of public good for rural areas (not for individual partners), prioritisation of public interest comparing with private interest.

Another tool to foster entrepreneurship, social economy and smart & short supply chains in Lithuania is the measure “*European Innovation Partnership – EIP*” of the RDP 2014–2020 programme. The Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania is responsible for implementation of this programme in the country. 50 proposals to apply to this measure were submitted from 2014 until 2021 and 28 projects were selected for implementation (56% of all submitted applications), for an overall amount of € 6,5 million (National Paying Agency, 30 May 2022).

Within the RDP 2014–2020 programme of Lithuania, the specific measure for short supply chains is called “*Support for the promotion of short supply chains and local markets at local level*”. The implementation of this measure lays under the responsibility of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania. 64 proposals of this measure have been submitted from 2014 until 2021 and 24 projects were selected for implementation (37,5% of all submitted applications). The total amount for funding amounted to € 2,2 million (National Paying Agency, 30 May 2022).

Examples of actions taken by local actors. Every year, several initiatives and projects are implemented in rural areas of Lithuania to support rural residents, encourage visitors to use new services and strengthen the local economy. The table below provides some examples.

Name of the initiative/project	Time of implementation	Contact & Internet address
Association “Viva Sol” – a new form of rural entrepreneurship via a diversified rural economy	Since the year 2006 - ongoing	Darguziai village, Varėna Municipality, Lithuania https://vivasol.lt/IN-ENGLISH/
"Village to Home" – project for the two-sided short food supply chain platform	Since the year 2013-ongoing	https://www.kaimasinamus.lt/
Stories from Pociūnėliai. Rural goods from Pociūnėliai (in Lithuanian: Pociūnėlių istorijos. Kaimiškos gėrybės iš Pociūnėlių). Initiative on short supply chain: farmers had surplus production, so they have started to produce candy, squeeze juices, dry fruits and herbs	Since the year 2019-ongoing	https://www.facebook.com: Pociūnėlių istorijos. Kaimiškos gėrybės iš Pociūnėlių
Salon of Krakiai community (in Lithuanian: Krakių bendruomenės svetainė) - is a community business that opened its doors		

<p>in June 2020. The place was created aiming to offer a cosy attraction center in a small town for both locals and guests, for whom they can offer delicious food, drinks, full shelves of local products and rich culinary and cultural heritage educational programs</p>	<p>Since the year 2020-ongoing</p>	<p>https://www.krakiusvetaine.lt/</p>
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4.3. Recommendations from the MAP

MAP experts have discussed on recommendations for future rural policies and future research agendas towards entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains. Results are provided in the next two sections.

4.3.1. Recommendations for future rural policies

Experts have provided recommendation for future rural policies that can be implemented at the local, regional and/or national level.

Recommendations at the local/regional level:

1. *Need of provision of services* not only to rural inhabitants but also to external visitors. This can bring additional financial resources to the region.
2. *Diversification of funding.* Community funding must act as a catalyst. Use not only national and the EU funds but also various other funds from private organisations, cooperation and co-creation initiatives, etc.
3. *Increasing demand to provide social services as alternative services* to rural inhabitants related with changes in public service provisions policy when the number of services provided by state are decreasing (in form of closure of schools, hospitals, post offices, etc.) and it is expected that rural communities should provide these services to rural inhabitants. Need for development of alternative services.
4. *Best practice examples and knowledge exchange* from neighbouring communities in Lithuania and other countries as a tool to get inspiring ideas for local community, LAGs, etc.
5. *Simpler approach for creation of services.* It was mentioned by experts that in Lithuania is very common to create a 'perfect' business and/or service. This is also a consequence of the requirements asked to service providers from the state institutions, that are very strict and in some cases bring demotivation for creation of these activities. It was suggested that education and good practice examples from other countries could help to revise expectations.
6. *Increase investment in human capital* to increase number of leaders and/or entrepreneurs in rural communities. This also is related with new functions to rural communities to provide social services for rural inhabitants.
7. Use *potential of 'slow villages/tourism'* in Lithuania. This type of activity gives opportunity to use most of local resources.
8. *Activate local politicians.* Recently they are very inactive and unmotivated. Their role on various activities at local level are very insignificant but expectations from rural communities are high as they want more active participation.

It was also stressed again, that it is necessary to decrease the level of bureaucracy and to increase trust in local communities and leaders, as well as their ideas.

Recommendations at the national level:

1. Assessment of the projects should be organised with *a higher focus on results* and not financial figures. The *result is more important than the process*.
2. *Diversification of funding*. Planning of funding should include representatives from different ministries as many of the activities cover responsibilities/functions from various ministries (e.g. Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Economics and Innovation, Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Lithuania, etc). Several national funds for rural development should be used and the EU funds too.
3. Decrease conflicting perspectives between *requirements for financial rules* from the EU/national funds and *possibilities to implement unique ideas*. Avoid a list with activities/services and that only this list of activities can be supported. Creation of principles on how to calculate the average price for service/item when there is no previous statistical data.
4. *Decrease bureaucratic burden at the EU level*. It was mentioned that the bureaucratic processes of the European Commission are very time-consuming and demanding. The new delivery model is very challenging. Inter-institutional communication and negotiations are difficult. Precise guidelines decrease the possibility to find their own way for the preparation of programmes, tools, measures, etc.
5. *Decrease bureaucratic burden at the national level*. Preparation of reports and implementation of other administrative requirements cannot take more time than the implementation of the project activities.
6. *Higher funding from national funds*. Recent state policy for rural development in Lithuania is focusing mostly on the use of EU funds and co-financing part. Experts have identified that the state should devote more national funds for project implementation in rural areas. This is related to changes in public service provisions policy when the number of services provided by the state is decreasing (in form of closure of schools, hospitals, post offices, etc.) and it is expected that rural communities should provide these services to rural inhabitants.
7. *Implementation of "smart" concept without a pre-defined framework*. Pre-defined frameworks and activities might decrease the number of original and unique ideas that are not possible to implement by following the rules of programming documents.
8. *Revise/decrease requirements for service providers from state institutions*. Some requirements for a place, food, and hygienic situation in the building are very high (e.g. from State Food and Veterinary Service institution). Experts have shared their experience that requirements can demotivate rural inhabitants and communities initiate social businesses or other activities because of requirements and attitudes from state institutions.
9. *Priority to support the idea*, and not a project. Experts have suggested that the selection committee should focus to select unique project ideas and support the implementation rather than focusing on project assessment where the only list of eligible activities are listed and not unique ideas and implementation of it. Identify when expert assessment is needed to evaluate the uniqueness of ideas, etc. aiming to avoid similar projects, activities, etc.

Experts gave a special attention to the need to improve project evaluation. This could be done, for instance, by focusing more on results and process (i.e. how the project is planned to be implemented: with partners, involving, empowering rural populations, but not on some formal 'created job places for 5 years', etc). In other words, more attention should be paid to impacts, not to formal - and most often - meaningless figures, which often act as restricting factors to taking part in the competition.

4.3.2. Recommendations for future research agendas

Experts have suggested the following topics for future research agendas towards entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains:

- 1. Cost and/or amount of work for € 1 support from the EU and national funds.** It was highlighted by experts that LAGs and rural communities have a very high bureaucratic burden when it comes to the preparation of strategies, projects, and later their implementation. Most of the work is on a voluntary basis. Motivation to participate in these projects becomes a key issue, especially if a huge amount of work is just devoted to administrative requirements and not to real implementation of ideas and cooperation.
- 2. How to simplify the bureaucratic machine of the EU support?** Requirements for the preparation of Rural development programmes for the EU Member States are very time-consuming, standardisation of documents leads to strict rules for implementation of projects for rural actors and thus cooperation, co-creation and trust between actors from policy, science and society decrease. How to find a good balance between a good level of bureaucratic requirements and enough room for creativeness and initiatives?
- 3. Do rural regions need creative personnel/motivator, consultant/mentor?** Experts mentioned that inhabitants of rural areas might be less active and have lower possibilities for travel and information and/or exchange of best practices. Some of them work in other jobs and do not have enough time to investigate new potential actions and activities for their rural area. Sometimes rural inhabitants need external people that can help them to see their activities from different perspectives. Research on the need, role, and impact of creative personnel/motivator, consultant/mentor for rural regions can provide results on how planning tools for regional development can be adjusted/improved to boost the participation of rural actors (as LAGs, rural communities, farmers, cooperatives, etc.).

In addition, a few more research agendas appeared have been suggested by experts as reported below:

- Monitoring and analysis of Smart Villages projects;
- Implementing and monitoring the local food system model;
- Monitoring and analysis of organic and national quality children's feeding system and meals.

And, during the final meeting, some more research trends on-demand were listed by experts:

- Research on tourism resources in rural areas;
- Identifying and harnessing cultural and natural resources for the needs of rural communities;
- Volunteering, bureaucracy, and moral fatigue in rural development;
- Crises and uncertainty as accelerators for community development.

Conclusions

Smart rurality, smart villages, digitalisation, bioeconomy & short supply chains are main keywords for the desirable future of rural areas in Lithuania. Rural inhabitants, both individuals or members of organisations, are key players in implementation of various actions. Leaders and entrepreneurs are also engine for many other rural residents and act as motivators. In the period 2023–2027, words such as 'smart rurality', 'creation/strengthening of smart villages', increase of digitalisation and short supply chains are outlined as new expectations and needs for rural areas in Lithuania. In Lithuania, the creation of a new image for rural areas can be subdivided into three steps that help to highlight the evolution of these territories: i) 1st step, from 2007 to 2013, the focus has been on gathering experience for rural residents and communities and rebuilding, renovating, constructing and empowering community buildings (first businesses initiated by rural communities) and improving other infrastructure for the high quality living in rural areas; 2nd step, from 2014 to 2020, the work done involved gathering new ideas and creating social and community businesses; 3rd step, from 2021 to 2027, with a specific attention on creation of smart villages.

Recommendations at local level highlight the need to activate local politicians, diversify funding sources, invest in human capital, increase the demand for social services as alternative services, recognise the importance of best practices and knowledge exchange. Recommendation at the national level focus on the need to decrease the bureaucratic burden (including at EU level), diversify funding sources, support ideas and the implementation "smart" concept without pushing for a framework "too strictly defined".

Recommendations for future research agendas include the need to investigate the experiences and difficulties of rural actors when preparing their vision for rural areas; and how the bureaucratic burden affect the motivation of LAGs and rural communities when defining their strategies, projects and later during the implementation phase. Research on need, role and impact of creative personnel/motivator, consultant/mentor for rural regions also is needed as it could help to understand how planning tools for regional development can be adjusted/improved in order to boost the participation of rural actors (as LAGs, rural communities, farmers, cooperatives, etc.).

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Annex 1 Methodology used by the MAP

This position paper was prepared using a six-step Delphi method, combining research, utilisation of quantitative data with expert interviews in Focus group meeting and surveys.

The following 6 steps were applied for this paper:

Step 1. Desk research and context analysis. Analysis was performed on March-April 2022.

Step 2. Interviews using one focus group meeting. Focus meetings was organised in May 2022. 14 MAP members (also called "experts") attended this meeting. The second in-person meeting took place on 26 May 2020.

Programme of the Focus group meeting is provided bellow.

9:50–10:00	Registration
10:00-10:10	Welcome words <i>dr. Rasa Melnikienė, Director of Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Institute of Economics and Rural development</i>
10:10–10:50	Entrepreneurship and the social economy in Lithuania and the EU regions: needs, challenges and necessary scientific-practical and political intervention <i>dr. Rita Lankauskienė, dr. Živilė Gedminaitė-Raudonė, Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Institute of Economics and Rural development</i>
10:50 –11:20	The importance of local communities to the social economy of the region <i>Virginija Šetkienė, Chairperson of Association of Rural Communities of Lithuania</i>
11:20 – 11:50	Coffee break
11:50 – 12:20	The roadmap towards a smart village <i>Kristina Švedaitė, Chairperson of Network of Local Action Groups of Lithuania</i>
12:20 – 12:50	Discussion (1st question): <i>What are the needs of the area covered by the MAP in relation entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains?</i>
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00-14:30	Discussion (2nd question): <i>What are the policy interventions already in place, and what are examples of actions taken by local actors addressing these needs implemented on the area covered by the MAP?</i>
14:30-15:00	Discussion (3rd question): <i>Which policy interventions (i.e. instruments, measures) are recommended by MAP members to be implemented at the local, regional, and/or national level? How can the EU support these interventions?</i>
15:00-15:30	Discussion (4th question): <i>What are the knowledge gaps and what research projects are needed?</i>

15:30-16:00	Conclusions and insights
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Step 3. Interview analysis, writing MAP Position paper and preparation of the survey. All tasks from Step 3 were performed on May-July 2022.

Step 4. MAP survey took place on August 2022. Experts completed the survey questionnaire using an online digital survey tool (Link: <http://www.apklausa.lt>).

A developed survey questionnaire for the Lithuanian case is provided in Annex 2.

Step 5. Survey analysis was completed on September 2022.

Step 6. Validation of results was organised on September 22, 2022 (Consensus meeting, virtual).

The process followed by the MAP of Lithuania is in line with SHERPA methodology, no changes were applied. MAP members have received an invitation to the Focus group meeting with a letter confirming the selected topic for 2022. The list of MAP members was updated at the beginning of 2022 by inviting them to join this group of experts that are well experienced in this topic. 4 new members joined the MAP. As result, during the 3rd MAP cycle, the MAP of Lithuania had 20 experts in total who have contributed to development of this Position Paper. Members were open to sharing experiences. Large discussions were for the policy intervention section with active participation from policy and NGOs representing rural communities and LAGs. Insights and experiences from the past were used for the formulation of recommendations for future policies and research agendas. Some take-up of results by MAP members was initiated after the meeting: increased cooperation between politicians and society (e.g. by inviting members of NGOs from LAGs and rural communities to take part in events organised by the Lithuanian parliament to share their experiences on this topic and other initiatives).

Annex 2 Lithuanian MAP survey questionnaire

Towards Sustainable & Resilient Value Chains

A warm welcome to a survey conducted by the Horizon 2020 Sherpa project

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear respondent,

The Sherpa project (rural-interfaces.eu) cordially invites you to participate in a survey to identify the key challenges and opportunities, enablers and hinderers in rural Lithuania in the field of entrepreneurship and social economy of rural areas, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains.

The survey contains 'quick click' multiple choice questions. The estimated time for completion is about 15 minutes.

Your responses are anonymous and confidential. They will be analysed and presented to a Lithuanian expert group – the so-called Multi-Actor Platform. The results will also be shared with the European Commission and as a contribution to its Long-term vision for rural areas.

Your feedback is important and we greatly appreciate you taking the time to complete this survey.

Thank you!

1. From the options below, which one describes your background best? Please choose only one option

- Public Sector / National Level
- Public Sector / Local Level
- NGO / Civil Society
- Business
- Research
- Private person

A group of experts and different societal actors from the Lithuanian Multi-Actor Platform discussed many themes and topics they consider to be relevant for rural areas in the field of entrepreneurship and social economy of rural areas, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains in Lithuania. The next questions allow you to state how important you perceive the topics to be and also rank them.

Actors in the development of rural areas in Lithuania

2. On a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) how important are these actors in the development of rural areas in Lithuania?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Important	Fairly important	Very important
Individual level actors:					
<i>local residents</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>farmers</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>local entrepreneurs</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
Organisational level:					
<i>rural communities</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>LAGs</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>associations</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
public organisations (as municipalities, ministries)	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please, specify):

3. Local leaders and entrepreneurs are the engine for many other rural residents and act as motivators

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with this statement.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Rural communities and LAGs take a very important role as intermediaries between local residents and public organisations that are responsible for rural policy implementation and coordination in Lithuania

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with this statement.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. Rural communities are the heart and engine of rural areas in Lithuania

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with this statement.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

New needs and existing initiatives

6. Recent challenges concerning the entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains in Lithuania

How important are the challenges below?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Important	Fairly important	Very important
<i>Lack of trust from public authorities in rural communities and LAGs. This is related to activities on project implementation by rural communities and LAGs.</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>High bureaucratic burden. It decreases initiatives from rural inhabitants and/or communities.</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Availability and amount of voluntary time spend on rural community initiatives. Not enough financial resources to cover the costs of personnel who prepare and implement projects by LAGs in rural areas. It can be expected to receive good project results when you have a sufficient amount of time and worse results with a lower amount of time spend on it.</i>	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please, specify)

7. Recent needs for communities of rural areas in Lithuania

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the below listed needs for communities of rural areas in Lithuania.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Guidelines for implementation of the 'Smart villages' concept in Lithuania.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creation of 'Smart Village' strategies that will reflect the challenges and needs of their territory by building on their local strengths and assets.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Trust in initiation and implementation of various actions and projects from public authorities to rural communities and LAGs.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Steps to decrease bureaucratic burden, especially for LAGs.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Use of opportunities for networking and cooperation. Steps to create real cooperation and not only an image of it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Search for solutions to motivate leaders of rural communities aiming to avoid the decrease in interest and not to be tired of activities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Care of communities as cells of body aiming good functioning of it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality of services in rural areas. Optimisation of costs needs to find other solutions (closing of schools, post offices, hospitals, etc.). Role of rural communities in the provision of these services initiated by public authorities as new functions (logistic, administration, management, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please, specify)					

8. Considering the understanding of Smart Villages in Lithuania

Discussions in expert groups and different societal actors from the Lithuanian Multi-Actor Platform accelerated to formulate the concept of Smart Villages in Lithuania as following:

"Smart Villages in Lithuania search smart solutions for rural areas that meet the needs of local residents by creating a long-term vision based on ideas proposed by scientists and innovative technologies."

The principle of 'being smart' focuses on the increase of attractiveness of rural areas, entrepreneurship, and creation of necessary infrastructure, use of cooperation and creation of stronger relations with neighbours.

'The Smart' can be concluded as 'receiving what you want' and 'achieving what you need'. This principle can reflect the needs of all actors that take part in the development of rural areas.

Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the formulated understanding of Smart Villages in Lithuania.

Agree

Disagree:

In case You disagree with the proposed aim of Smart Villages in Lithuania, please suggest an alternative formulation:

9. Smart solutions in rural areas

Smart solutions require:

Not at all important Slightly important Important Fairly important Very important

enough time for creativity

critical situations

An example is the recent pandemic situation – it has opened up many new opportunities as before communities were not even thinking that some challenges can be overcome in one or another way

thinking "out of the box" (non-standard way)

starting from yourself

Existing interventions and actions

10. Encouraging measures for entrepreneurship and social economy of rural areas, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains in Lithuania

In the new programming period from 2022 to 2027, 5 topics are selected by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania that are able encourage and increase the entrepreneurship and social economy of rural areas, just transition and sustainable & resilient value chains in Lithuania.

Please indicate to what extent the proposed 5 topics would be helpful in Lithuania:

Topics for 2022 - 2027	Not helpful at all	Neither helpful nor hindering	Very helpful
6. Projects for local economy: a. Economic diversification and rural tourism; b. Short supply chains and local food systems.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Projects for creation of inclusive local infrastructure and services: a. Social networks and other e-platforms for information exchange, e-public services; b. Social service centres, the House of Generations; c. Science-based innovative education, training and consultation; d. Solutions for smart green infrastructure.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Projects for smart governance: a. Provision of public administration services remotely (on-line); b. Digitalised work of community and feed-back using digital tools; c. Development of organisational reflexes, optimisation of activities and increase of efficiency.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. Projects for smart rural community: a. Ability to accumulate and use local intangible resources for the benefit of local residents and business development; b. Digital skills and use of digital technologies; c. Cooperation and networking; development of management tools for cooperation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. Projects for environment protection and climate change mitigation: a. Sustainable use of natural resources and restoration (smart use); b. Solutions to solve food wasting problems; c. Waste management; d. Renewable energy; e. Agroecology and agro environment.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other, if missing (please, specify):

Recommendations from the MAP

11. Recommendations for future rural policies *at the local/regional level*

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the below listed summarised recommendations:

<u>Recommendations at the local/regional level:</u>	Not at all important	Slightly important	Important	Fairly important	Very important
<i>Activate local politicians.</i> Recently they are very inactive and unmotivated. Their role in various activities at the local level is very insignificant but expectations from rural communities are high as they want more active participation.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Diversification of funding.</i> Community funding must act as a catalyst. Use not only national and EU funds but also various other funds from private organisations, cooperation and co-creation initiatives, etc.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Increase investment in human capital</i> aiming to increase the number of leaders and/or entrepreneurs in rural communities. This also is related to new functions in rural communities to provide social services for rural inhabitants.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Need for provision of services</i> not only to rural inhabitants but also to external visitors. This can bring additional financial resources to the region.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Increasing demand to provide social services as alternative services</i> to rural inhabitants is related to changes in public service provisions policy when the number of services provided by the state is decreasing (in form of closure of schools, hospitals, post offices, etc.) and it is expected that rural communities should provide these services to rural inhabitants. Need for development of alternative services.	<input type="radio"/>				
Use the <i>potential of 'slow villages/tourism'</i> in Lithuania. This type of activity gives the opportunity to use most of the local resources.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Best practice examples and knowledge exchange</i> from neighboring communities in Lithuania and other countries as a tool to get inspiring ideas for the local community, LAGs, etc.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>A simpler approach for the creation of services.</i> It was mentioned by experts that in Lithuania is a very common practice and approach to creating a 'perfect' business and/or service. This also is affected by the requirements	<input type="radio"/>				

for service providers from state institutions that are very strict and in some cases demotivation for the creation of these activities. It was suggested that education and good practice examples from other countries could help to revise expectations.

Other, if not mentioned (please, specify)

12. Recommendations for future rural policies *at the national level*

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the below listed summarised recommendations:

Recommendations at the national level:

Not at all important Slightly important Important Fairly important Very important

Decrease bureaucratic burden at the EU level.

Bureaucratic processes of the EC are very time-consuming and demanding. The new delivery model is very challenging. Interinstitutional communication is difficult. Negotiations are difficult. Precise instructions decrease the possibility to find their own way for the preparation of programmes, tools, measures, etc.

Decrease bureaucratic burden at the national level.

Preparation of reports and implementation of other administrative requirements cannot take more time than the implementation of the project activities.

Decrease conflicting perspectives between *requirements for financial rules* from the EU/national funds and *possibilities to implement unique ideas*. Avoid a list with activities/services that only this list of activities can be supported. Creation of principles on how to calculate the average price for service/item when there is no previous statistical data.

Assessment of the projects with a *higher focus on results* and not financial figures. The *result is more important than the process*.

Revise/decrease requirements for service providers from state institutions. Some requirements for a place, food, and hygienic situation in the building are very high (for example, from State Food and Veterinary Service institution). Experts have shared their experience that requirements can demotivate rural inhabitants and communities initiate social businesses or other activities because of requirements and attitudes from state institutions.

Priority to support the idea, and not a project. Experts have suggested that the selection committee should focus to select unique project ideas and giving light to implementing them instead of focusing on project assessment where the only list of eligible activities are listed and not unique ideas and implementation of it. Identify need when expert assessment is needed aiming to evaluate the uniqueness of ideas, etc. aiming to avoid similar projects, activities, etc.

Implementation of "smart" concept without a defined framework. A defined framework and activities might decrease the number of original and unique ideas that are not possible to implement by following the rules of programming documents.

Diversification of funding. Planning of funding should include representatives from different ministries as many of the activities cover responsibilities/functions from various ministries (for example, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Economics and Innovation, Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Lithuania, etc). Use of various national funds for rural development should be used and the EU funds too.

Higher funding from national funds. Recent state policy for rural development in Lithuania is focusing mostly on the use the EU funds and co-financing part. Experts have identified that states should devote more national funds for project implementation in rural areas. This is related to changes in public service provisions policy when the number of services provided by the state is decreasing (in form of closure of schools, hospitals, post offices, etc.) and it is expected that rural communities should provide these services to rural inhabitants.

Other, if not mentioned (please, specify)

13. Recommendations for future research agendas

Please indicate to what extent the proposed research agendas would help develop the topic further in Lithuania:

Future research topics

Not helpful at all

Neither helpful nor hindering

Very helpful

Cost and/or amount of work for 1 EUR support from the EU and national funds.

The bureaucratic burdens for LAGs and rural communities remain very high for the preparation of strategies, projects, and later implementation of it. Most of the work is done voluntarily. The question is about motivation to participate in the projects if a huge amount of work is devoted to administrative

requirements and not for real activities/implementation of ideas/cooperation and so on.

How to simplify the bureaucratic machine of the EU support?

This proposal is related to the first topic – requirements for preparation of Rural development programmes for the EU member states are very time-consuming, standardisation of documents leads to strict rules for implementation of projects for rural actors and thus cooperation, co-creation and trust between actors from policy, science and society decrease. How to find a good combination of sufficient amount for requirements and enough room for creativeness and initiatives?

Do rural regions need creative personnel/motivator, consultant/mentor?

Inhabitants of rural areas might be less active and have lower possibilities for travel and information and/or best practice exchange. Some of them are working in other jobs and do not have enough time to investigate new potential actions and activities for their rural area. Sometimes rural inhabitants need some personnel from outside that can help to see their activities from different perspectives. Research on the need, role and impact of creative personnel/motivator, consultant/mentor for rural regions can provide results on how planning tools for regional development can be adjusted/improved aiming to get desirable results for rural areas with the participation of rural actors (as LAGs, rural communities, farmers, cooperatives, etc.).

Other (please, specify):

14. Anything else to add?

Do you have any comments?

Towards Sustainable & Resilient Value Chains

THANK YOU !

Thank you very much for your time!

Results will be made available in September 2022.

Any questions? Contact:

Rita Lankauskienė: rita.lankauskiene@ekvi.lt

Živilė Gedminaitė-Raudonė: zivile.gedminaitė@ekvi.lt

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Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

www.rural-interfaces.eu

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